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THE PARADOX OF UMBRELLA CLAUSES: BALANCING STATE INTERFERENCE AND INVESTOR PROTECTION IN AFRICA'S INVESTMENT FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the paradox of umbrella clauses in Africa's investment framework, highlighting their role in balancing state sovereignty and investor protection. Typically included in bilateral investment treaties (BITs), these clauses mandate host states to honor their commitments to foreign investors. While they serve as a crucial safeguard for investors, umbrella clauses have sparked significant controversy due to varying interpretations by scholars and arbitral tribunals. This inconsistency has led many African governments to overlook, amend, or revoke their international obligations, resulting in a surge of investor-state disputes across the continent. The paper aims to elucidate the complexities surrounding the umbrella clause by analyzing the motivations behind African governments' engagement with BITs and their contractual relationships with foreign investors. Through this examination, it seeks to address the interpretive challenges and enhance understanding of the umbrella clause's implications for investment protection in African states.

Keywords: *Umbrella Provision, African states Investment, International Investment Agreements, Investment Protection and State interference, Legal Frameworks*

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INTRODUCTION

Bilateral investment treaties (BITs) have transformed international investment law, attracting foreign capital and facilitating international arbitration.¹ The “umbrella clause” in BITs mandates each Contracting State to uphold investment-related obligations towards investors from other states.² Recent adjudications by the International Centre for the Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID) have sparked debates about its applicability to autonomous investment contracts. The flow of capital from developed nations to developing nations has led to a tendency for developing nations to interpret BIT provisions restrictively, causing friction between the two blocs regarding foreign investment. Proponents argue that the interpretation of umbrella clauses favors developed nations, disadvantaging developing countries, which often have diminished leverage in BIT negotiations. However, the presence of an exclusive forum selection clause within an investment contract may unjustly penalize investors, perpetuating inequities within the international investment landscape. Such endeavors are encapsulated in formal bilateral agreements, which may include development contracts, tax stabilization accords, concessions pertaining to public services, investment treaties, and similar instruments. Investors, in varying degrees, predicate their decisions regarding the allocation of capital within a host jurisdiction upon these commitments and undertakings. This phenomenon is predominantly facilitated through the enforcement of umbrella clauses enshrined in treaties. Such provisions constitute a prevalent strategy employed by the African states to attract foreign investments.

THE NOTION OF UMBRELLA CLAUSE(UC)

The UC is not clear in the terms of definition is concern. The UC in an investment treaty requires the host state to fulfil its commitments to protect the foreign investor.³ Now the question of obligation is subject to further discussion, what are the obligations and how to enforce under the BITs or Multilateral agreement is subject to further deliberation and in the course of discussion this paper attempt to shed light on to this given doctrine. These clauses derive their nomenclature from the metaphorical function of providing a protective canopy under which contractual and ancillary

- 1 Stefan Eichler and Jannik André Nauerth, ‘Bilateral Investment Treaties and Portfolio Investment’ (2024) 91 *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money* 101918.
- 2 CL Lim, ‘Is the Umbrella Clause Not Just Another Treaty Clause?’ in CL Lim (ed), *Alternative Visions of the International Law on Foreign Investment: Essays in Honour of Muthucumaraswamy Sornarajah* (Cambridge University Press 2016) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/alternative-visions-of-the-international-law-on-foreign-investment/is-the-umbrella-clause-not-just-another-treaty-clause/DCA1314D492BB7702D991CBC1D2442D8>> accessed 30 September 2024.
- 3 Anthony C Sinclair, ‘The Origins of the Umbrella Clause in the International Law of Investment Protection’ (2004) 20 *Arbitration International* 411.

commitments are subsumed within the treaty’s safeguarding framework. In addition to the UC “observance of undertaking clauses,”⁴ is also employed in IIAs which emphasizes their function in enforcement by the host state’s enforcement of its duties. The state’s failure to fulfill a contract does not immediately bind it to direct international obligation.⁵ Nonetheless, several recent bilateral investment treaty portions have been referred to be “umbrella clauses” by some courts operating under the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID).⁶ By forcing each party to perform their obligations with regard to investments made by other contractual parties within their jurisdiction, these clauses seek to offer complete protection for foreign investors.⁷

THE PARADOX OF UMBRELLA CLAUSE PROTECTIONS

The “umbrella clause,” which is present in many bilateral investment treaties (BITs) and mandates that each Contracting State fulfill all investment-related commitments towards investors from other Contracting States, has given rise to a contentious arbitration issue. The inconsistent implementation of seemingly similar umbrella provisions by different courts raises serious concerns about the evolution and consistency of investment treaty law. The diversity of arbitral rulings pertaining to this Article has undoubtedly been influenced by the multiplicity of interpretations that tribunals have encountered in different situations. Arbitration has become more acrimonious in recent years, especially when it comes to interpreting the previously stated “umbrella clause.” This clause requires all Contracting States to uphold their duties regarding investments made with investors from other Contracting States. A significant investigation of whether the umbrella clause covers duties emerging from independent investment treaties between the investor and the host State has been sparked by two recent ICSID rulings, *SGS v.*

4 Olivia Danic, ‘L’Émergence D’Un Droit International Des Investissements - Contribution Des Traités Bilatéraux D’Investissement et de La Jurisprudence Du CIRDI’ <https://www.academia.edu/48621197/L%C3%A9mergence_dun_droit_international_des_investissements_Contribution_des_trait%C3%A9s_bilat%C3%A9raux_dinvestissement_et_de_la_jurisprudence_du_CIRDI> accessed 30 September 2024.

5 Yuliya Chernykh, ‘Chapter 1 Overview of Contract Interpretation in Investment Treaty Arbitration’ (Brill 2022) <<https://brill.com/display/book/9789004414709/BP000003.xml>> accessed 30 September 2024.

6 Andrea K Bjorklund, ‘The Legitimacy of the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes’ in Andreas Follesdal and others (eds), *Legitimacy and International Courts* (Cambridge University Press 2018) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/legitimacy-and-international-courts/legitimacy-of-the-international-centre-for-settlement-of-investment-disputes/A5F9D244B9C38EDDBF2B234023171E6A>> accessed 30 September 2024.

7 Zachary Douglas KC, ‘The Umbrella Clause Revisited’ (2023) 38 ICSID Review - Foreign Investment Law Journal 472.

*Pakistan*⁸ and *SGS v. Philippines*⁹. Under such an interpretation, the investor would be able to pursue remedies for any violations relating to investment contracts through the international arbitration process outlined in the BIT, since the international arbitration tribunal created under the BIT would have the authority to decide cases involving breach of contract. However, different interpretations of the umbrella clause have resulted from the SGS rulings, practically nullifying it. This article attempts to address two main questions raised by the SGS rulings viz;

first, does a BIT tribunal have jurisdiction over claims of breach of contract based on the argument that the umbrella clause applies to investor-state contracts?

Secondly, even if the BIT tribunal has jurisdiction, can it still assert it in cases where the contract in question has an exclusive forum selection clause that designates a different forum for the resolution of contractual disputes? In *SGS v. Pakistan*,¹⁰ a Swiss company signed a contract in 1994, whereas SGS argued in this arbitration process that Pakistan had violated the terms of the contract pertaining to SGS's supply of pre-shipment inspection services by engaging in wrongful repudiation or illegal termination. The tribunal's job was to decide on the objections made about its authority to hear the case.¹¹

After many years, however, Pakistan terminated the arrangement due to dissatisfaction with SGS's performance. According to the PSI Agreement, Pakistan's activities were said to be in violation of the BITs between Switzerland and Pakistan. Investors cannot sue a host state under an umbrella clause based only on an alleged violation of contract, since the Tribunal made clear that a host state's non-treaty responsibilities do not equate to treaty obligations. Umbrella clauses only apply when a host state abuses its sovereign authority to breach a contract, according to the ruling in *El Paso v. Argentina*.¹² This method was supported by a number of instances, including

8 'SGS Société Générale de Surveillance S.A. v. Islamic Republic of Pakistan, ICSID Case No. ARB/01/13 | Italaw' <<https://www.italaw.com/cases/1009>> accessed 30 September 2024.

9 'SGS v. Philippines, Decision of the Tribunal on Objections to Jurisdiction, 29 Jan 2004' <<https://jsumundi.com/en/document/decision/en-sgs-societe-generale-de-surveillance-s-a-v-republic-of-the-philippines-decision-of-the-tribunal-on-objections-to-jurisdiction-thursday-29th-january-2004>> accessed 30 September 2024.

10 Martin Lau, 'Note on Société Générale de Surveillance SA v. Pakistan, through Secretary, Ministry of Finance' (2003) 19 *Arbitration International* 179.

11 'SGS v. Pakistan | Investment Dispute Settlement Navigator | UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub' <<https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-dispute-settlement/cases/70/sgs-v-pakistan>> accessed 29 September 2024.

12 Gabriel Cavazos Villanueva, 'El Paso Energy International Company v Argentine Republic' (2012) 27 *ICSID Review - Foreign Investment Law Journal* 27.

Siemens v. Argentina,¹³ *Joy Mining v. Egypt*,¹⁴ *Salini v. Jordan*,¹⁵ and *Toto Construzioni v. Lebanon*.¹⁶ In contrast to its predecessor, the ICSID Tribunal in *SGS v. Philippines* viewed the bilateral investment treaty's umbrella clause differently. The Tribunal reasoned that while the duties of a state regarding a particular investment are enforceable under domestic law, the umbrella clause incorporates such obligations within the treaty framework. The Tribunal's interpretation of the Umbrella Clause gives it the power to examine matters involving alleged non-treaty duties under local legislation, so broadening its jurisdiction. A similar tactic was used in *BIVAC v. Paraguay* and *Bosh v. Ukraine*. The Umbrella Clause transforms a host state's non-treaty responsibilities into treaty obligations, placing them within the *ratione materiae*¹⁷ jurisdiction of an arbitral tribunal for investment treaties, as the Tribunal in *SGS v. Paraguay* emphasized.

Nevertheless, in the case *Eureko v. Poland*¹⁸ the arbitration found that the host state's breach of its commercial responsibilities might be interpreted as a treaty infringement since it compromised the state's need to fulfill its obligations with regard to the claimant's investments.

The cases of *Noble Ventures v. Romania*¹⁹ and *Burlington v. Ecuador*²⁰ brought to light how umbrella clauses might be interpreted to convert local legal duties into obligations under international law. This prompted questions about whether the Bilateral Investment Treaty's umbrella clause may be broken by Investor-State contracts and if BIT courts have the authority to hear

13 Jus Mundi, 'Siemens v. Argentina, Decision on Jurisdiction, 3 Aug 2004' <<https://jusmundi.com/en/document/decision/en-siemens-a-g-v-the-argentine-republic-decision-on-jurisdiction-tuesday-3rd-august-2004>> accessed 30 September 2024.

14 N Gallus, 'Joy Mining v. Egypt: No Joy for British Mining Equipment Company at the ICSID' (2004) 1 Transnational Dispute Management (TDM) <<https://www.transnational-dispute-management.com/article.asp?key=290>> accessed 30 September 2024.

15 JP Gaffney, 'Case Summary - Salini Costruttori S.p.A. and Italstrade S.p.A.-v- The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan (ICSID Case No. ARB/02/13)' (2005) 2 Transnational Dispute Management (TDM) <<https://www.transnational-dispute-management.com/article.asp?key=375>> accessed 30 September 2024.

16 'Toto v. Lebanon | Investment Dispute Settlement Navigator | UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub' <<https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-dispute-settlement/cases/264/toto-v-lebanon>> accessed 30 September 2024.

17 Aaron X Fellmeth and Maurice Horwitz, 'Ratione Materiae', *Guide to Latin in International Law* (Oxford University Press 2011) <<https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/acref/9780195369380.001.0001/acref-9780195369380-e-1791>> accessed 30 September 2024.

18 'Eureko BV v. Republic of Poland' (2007) 12 ICSID Reports 331.

19 'Noble Ventures Inc. v. Romania' (2012) 16 ICSID Reports 210.

20 Jason Rudall, 'The Tribunal with a Toolbox: On Perenco v Ecuador, Black Gold and Shades of Green' (2020) 11 Journal of International Dispute Settlement 485.

cases involving contract violations. As a result, host nations have made many changes to African BITs.

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE UMBRELLA CLAUSE BY THE AFRICAN STATES

Investment treaties in African nations are increasingly incorporating the “umbrella clause” to protect foreign investors’ interests and boost their confidence in investing.²¹ These clauses require host states to fulfil their contractual commitments to foreign investors, attracting international capital. South Africa’s Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) include stipulations mandating contractual parties to fulfil their obligations to foreign investors, such as the Iran-South Africa Bilateral Investment Treaty. Tanzania has entered into multiple BITs with countries like China, Canada, Denmark, Germany, and the United Kingdom, reinforcing its commitment to meeting its obligations. The incorporation of umbrella clauses in these treaties reflects a broader trend among African nations to provide a more favourable investment climate. By treating contractual obligations as treaty obligations, these clauses aim to mitigate risks, foster a stable market for FDI, and promote economic growth in this region.

THE INTERTWINE OF STATE RESPONSIBILITY AND INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION

When a state violates an international obligation, and by wrongful act it considered to be invoke the issue of state of responsibility. Investment contracts are typically domestic agreements governed by local law, not international treaties.²²

Disputes arising from contract breaches are typically resolved within national courts. However, some investment treaties can extend protections to foreign investors by elevating specific contractual obligations to international commitments. A contract violation can be considered a treaty violation if the investor’s rights are compromised, underscoring the complexity of international investment law, as the intersection of national contractual duties and treaty protections significantly impacts investor remedies.

However, concerns about the proneness of investment contracts to unfavorable changes in the law of the host countries have led some academics to speculate that these contracts may be removed from the national legal

21 Matthias Herdegen, ‘Treaties on Investment Protection’ in Matthias Herdegen (ed), *Principles of International Economic Law*, 3e (Oxford University Press 2024) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/law/9780198897835.003.0035>> accessed 30 September 2024.

22 Sondra Faccio, ‘Investment Contracts and the Reform of Investment Arbitration: Towards Sustainability’ (2023) 38 ICSID Review - Foreign Investment Law Journal 625.

system and placed under the shield of international law. This theoretical shift, whereby contractual obligations are transmuted into international obligations, is referred to as “Internationalization.”²³ Such a process signifies that these contracts fall under the governance of customary international law rather than the local statutes of the state party involved. For example in the *Serbian Loans* casethat “any contract which is not a contract between States in their capacity as subjects of international law is based on the domestic law of some country.”²⁴ This court’s position was noteworthy. However, these kinds of agreements may be freed from the state party’s municipal laws and brought within the purview of an international legal supranational framework, which will protect the foreign investor’s economic interests and contractual rights. These contracts gain a level of stability that is vital for foreign investors by falling under the jurisdiction of international law. International law defines a breach as a state party’s interference or rescinding of a contract, potentially leading to inequitable treatment, license revocation, expropriation without just compensation, due process violations, or infringements of treaty norms.²⁵ Foreign investors establish international investment contracts with host states through Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs), outlining specific terms and conditions for investments within the host state’s territorial boundaries.

These agreements, which differ in form, structure, and model, provide effective and transparent communication between the parties.

STATE INTERVENTION INVESTMENT AGREEMENTS

The State’s encroachment upon international investment contracts is often manifested through executive edicts or legislative enactments that modify the obligations of the government as delineated within the contract, effectuate its termination, or detrimentally influence the anticipated profits or operational efficacy thereof. Such state interference may materialize through actions such as the expropriation of assets belonging to foreign investors without adequate compensation, the manipulation of judicial processes, or the contravention of

23 Jean Ho (ed), ‘State Responsibility and Internationalisation’, *State Responsibility for Breaches of Investment Contracts* (Cambridge University Press 2018) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/state-responsibility-for-breaches-of-investment-contracts/state-responsibility-and-internationalisation/7AEB4D49586538E61AC18F90E28CBABF>> accessed 29 September 2024.

24 Ioana Tudor, ‘The FET Standard, Part of the Body of General International Law’ in Ioana Tudor (ed), *The Fair and Equitable Treatment Standard in the International Law of Foreign Investment* (Oxford University Press 2008) <<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199235063.003.0003>> accessed 30 September 2024.

25 August Reinisch and Christoph Schreuer (eds), ‘Expropriation’, *International Protection of Investments: The Substantive Standards* (Cambridge University Press 2020) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/international-protection-of-investments/expropriation/16B683347D6D27C6FA99EE62C691A038>> accessed 30 September 2024.

salient treaty provisions, including but not limited to the Most Favoured Nation (MFN) clause or the principle of Fair and Equitable Treatment (FET).²⁶ It is pertinent to observe that, in the absence of extenuating circumstances such as an abuse of legal principles, a deficiency in due process, or evidence of discriminatory intent a state party shall not incur liability under international law for undertaking measures, such as amending laws of general applicability, which result in the encroachment upon a foreign investor's contractual rights with said state.

NON-COMPLIANCE AND INTERFERENCE BY AFRICAN STATES IN BITS.

To augment the allure of foreign investment through the provision of an enhanced layer of protection, a multitude of states have entered into BITs or other forms of IIAs, particularly in the context of a dearth of a comprehensive international treaty governing the regulation or safeguarding of foreign investment. Since a BIT provides certain guidelines and norms that apply to foreign investments, it serves as a primary tool for regulating and overseeing such ventures. BITs, or Best Interest Treatment Obligations, are laws that protect foreign investments through mechanisms like National Treatment Obligations and Most Favored Nation Treatment Obligations, ensuring appropriate procedures in case of contract disagreements.²⁷

Through the establishment of minimum standards and the provision of international arbitration for disputes, bilateral investment treaties (BITs) provide security and protection for foreign investments. By guaranteeing host nations' commitment to encouraging and protecting foreign investments, these accords reassure international investors. But not all countries abide by these treaties' provisions, especially the ones that pertain to African States. Under the aegis of ICSID, investor-state arbitrations predominate, and the number of conflicts has been steadily rising over time. ICSID has 869 cases involving state parties from Sub-Saharan Africa as of December 31, 2021.²⁸ Given the severity of these problems and the degree of treaty noncompliance by host governments, CSID is an essential point of reference.

REASONS AFRICAN STATE INTERFERE AND AVOID BITS

Treaty responsibilities are often not fulfilled due to various factors, including historical and sociopolitical backgrounds, economic

26 Anqi Wang, 'Chapter 1 History of the MFN Clause in International Law' (Brill 2022) <<https://brill.com/display/book/9789004517899/BP000002.xml>> accessed 30 September 2024.

27 Alejandro A Escobar, 'Philip Morris v. Uruguay (ICSID)' (2017) 56 International Legal Materials 1.

28 'The ICSID Caseload Statistics (2022-1 Edition) ENG.Pdf' <<https://icsid.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/Caseload%20Statistics%20Charts/The%20ICSID%20Caseload%20Statistics%20%282022-1%20Edition%29%20ENG.pdf>> accessed 30 September 2024.

considerations, political processes, institutional and legal frameworks, cultural influences, and external factors. African countries often view international treaties as tools of neocolonialism due to their history of colonialism and struggle with public health emergencies, inadequate infrastructure, and poverty reduction. Economic concerns, such as public health emergencies and inadequate infrastructure, can lead to regulatory actions that contradict BIT requirements. Political processes within governments can also impact treaty compliance, with frequent changes in ideology and governance leading to inconsistent adherence. Effective implementation of bilateral investment treaties (BITs) is often challenging due to deficiencies in institutional and legal frameworks, leading to opaque decision-making and arbitrary judgment. Cultural influences can also influence attitudes towards international treaties, leading to distrust and resistance to honoring obligations that benefit foreign parties at the cost of domestic interests. Additionally, external factors like the function of global financial institutions and geopolitical events can complicate treaty compliance, forcing nations to prioritize economic policies over BIT responsibilities. Therefore, understanding the intricacies of treaty non-fulfillment and developing strategies to promote compliance requires a comprehensive analysis of historical, economic, political, cultural, and external factors.

Adoption of Model Treaties

Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) are predominantly instigated and propelled towards fruition by capital-exporting home states, primarily those situated in the Western hemisphere.²⁹ This is because protecting the investments made abroad by their residents is imperative. The agreements are mostly based on precedent-setting treaties from the West.³⁰ Capital-exporting nations consider these clauses essential for safeguarding foreign investments, yet they do not impose any responsibilities on foreign investors. Because its instrument served as the foundation for negotiations, the adoption of model treaties gave states that export capital an advantage in negotiations. The host state negotiates with foreign governments from a vulnerable position, often opposing changes to model treaties. South Africa's Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) were found to be heavily skewed in favor of home governments and neglected to consider risks and rewards. The treaties were

29 Wilfred J Ethier, 'The Relevance of Ricardian Trade Theory for the Political Economy of Trade Policy' in Ronald W Jones and Rolf Weder (eds), *200 Years of Ricardian Trade Theory: Challenges of Globalization* (Springer International Publishing 2017) <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-60606-4_15> accessed 30 September 2024.

30 Pravin Krishna, 'Regional and Preferential Trade Agreements', *The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics* (Palgrave Macmillan UK 2018) <https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-349-95189-5_2447> accessed 30 September 2024.

silent on environmental and human rights issues and did not identify investor commitments, making host nations unwilling to fulfill their obligations. The CCIA and SADC Model Treaty,³¹ supported by Sub-Saharan African nations, aim to establish balanced investment agreements that are not biased towards international investors.³²

Regulatory Jurisdiction

Accordingly, in matters pertaining to foreign investments, the treaty took precedence over local laws. Furthermore, the extent to which investments are protected by the BITs is further restricted by the inclusion of administrative rights like licenses and permits as well as public legislation in the lists of investments. Consequently, the host African governments seek to reassert their regulatory authority over the economy, encompassing the domain of international investment. The Republic of the *Gambia v. African Petroleum*,³³ Gambia Limited case highlights the importance of local regulatory autonomy, as protected by the SADC Model BIT and CCIA through exemption clauses. State parties can also enforce measures for public morality, national security, human life, health, and environmental objectives, as specified in Article 22 (1) of the CCIA.³⁴

Circumstantial Changes

The preponderance of (BITs) was executed by the respective home and host governments in the immediate aftermath of the decolonization of various African republics.³⁵ Compared to the rest of the globe, Africa has different development demands after independence. These agreements have evolved over time to no longer represent the current concerns and demands of emerging host countries about investments and development. It is therefore essential that the BITs be changed.

31 'The SADC Model BIT Template: Investment for Sustainable Development – Investment Treaty News' <<https://www.iisd.org/itn/en/2012/10/30/the-sadc-model-bit-template-investment-for-sustainable-development/>> accessed 30 September 2024.

32 'Professor Uché Ewelukwa Ofodile - Articles by Author | TDM Journal' <<https://www.transnational-dispute-management.com/journal-author-articles.asp?key=2375>> accessed 29 September 2024.

33 'African Petroleum Gambia Limited (Block A1) v. Republic of The Gambia, ICSID Case No. ARB/14/6 | Itlaw' <<https://www.italaw.com/cases/2477>> accessed 30 September 2024.

34 Christian Riffel, 'indirect Expropriation and The Protection of Public Interests' (2022) 71 *International & Comparative Law Quarterly* 945.

35 William Woodruff, 'The Decolonization of Africa' in William Woodruff (ed), *A Concise History of the Modern World: 1500 to the Present* (Palgrave Macmillan UK 1998) <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-26663-0_16> accessed 30 September 2024.

Consideration of Public Interest

State parties have the power to modify or cancel agreements with foreign investors in order to achieve public policy goals; nevertheless, these measures cannot include compensation for reparation.³⁶ This is because a state party is seen as representing the interests of its people when signing an international investment treaty. Additionally, a state party can modify or terminate an agreement if circumstances change contrary to public interest, following the principle of 'rebus sic stantibus'.³⁷

The Pursuit of Nationalism

State parties consider their natural resources as sovereign assets essential to their economic development, especially in the energy sector.³⁸ The foundation of this viewpoint is customary international law, which places a strong emphasis on perpetual sovereignty over natural resources. A rising number of investment treaty lawsuits and arbitrations in the energy industry have resulted from African nations' nationalization of energy resources. This phenomenon is best illustrated by the Zimbabwean situation,³⁹ where conflicts between domestic interests and commitments to make foreign investments were brought to light by the eviction of white farmers and the nationalization of white-owned businesses. Government parties often defend nationalizations as essential for economic growth and empowerment, but these moves frequently result in disagreements with foreign investors and arbitration cases that call into question the legality of governmental involvement.⁴⁰ The African energy sector becomes a hotbed of conflict,⁴¹ symbolizing larger challenges that arise when governments put their sovereignty above adhering to international investment norms. States must carefully strike a balance between the need to use resources for domestic advantage and the potential fallout from investment treaty claims and arbitration proceedings.

36 Andrew T Guzman, 'The Design of International Agreements' (2005) 16 *European Journal of International Law* 579.

37 Brett A. Leeds and Burcu Savun, 'Terminating Alliances: Why Do States Abrogate Agreements?' (2007) Vol 69 *The Journal of Politics* 1118.

38 Cristian Timmermann and Eduardo Noboa, 'Energy Sovereignty: A Values-Based Conceptual Analysis' (2022) 28 *Science and Engineering Ethics* 54.

39 Yolanda T Chekera and Vincent O Nmehielle, 'The International Law Principle of Permanent Sovereignty over Natural Resources as an Instrument for Development: The Case of Zimbabwean Diamonds' <[https://brill.com /view/journals/ajls/6/1/article-p69_4.xml](https://brill.com/view/journals/ajls/6/1/article-p69_4.xml)> accessed 30 September 2024.

40 V Bijukumar, 'Economic Reforms, Populism and Party Politics in India' (2004) 65 *The Indian Journal of Political Science* 161.

41 Abdulkadir Shettima and others, 'The Impact of Conflict on Energy Poverty: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa' (2023) 86 *Resources Policy* 104090.

Restriction on Local Resources

African nations have modified their energy laws, rules, and bidding procedures to include “local content” requirements.⁴² As a result, they are gradually requiring foreign investors to abide by these standards. The goal of local content rules, which give preference to domestic companies over international ones, is to improve the skills of domestic workers and generate jobs in the area. Additionally, they encourage regional involvement in contract bidding procedures, which strengthens local businesses’ ability to compete. These rules support a strong supply chain that is less dependent on outside resources and boost the local economy. As part of their national petroleum laws, nations including Nigeria, Kenya, Ghana, Mozambique,⁴³ and Angola have imposed local content limitations in an effort to maximize the financial gains from international investment while preserving national sovereignty and promoting sustainable development. Local content regulations are an essential tool for supporting homegrown businesses and guaranteeing that the benefits of resource exploitation are distributed fairly within the country of hostility.

Justification for State Responsibility

The ratification of the treaty has led to the emergence of several defenses against state responsibility.⁴⁴ State parties rely on and make use of defenses to explain away their treaty violations. The purpose of these defenses is to give the state party an escape route from responsibility. Defenses against state accountability include those pertaining to national security. State parties in underdeveloped countries often use customary international law as justification for their regulatory jurisdiction over foreign investments. This argument is especially essential when dealing with issues like environmental degradation and breaches of human rights. The sovereign prerogative of state parties to control investments is asserted, particularly in cases when foreign investors compromise local human rights and environmental norms. They contend that if investment safeguards are seen to absolve investors of responsibility for damaging actions, the host state has the right to withdraw or restrict them. This resistance is part of a larger effort by developing nations to take control of local regulatory systems and mitigate the negative effects of foreign investment. State parties seek to supersede responsibilities under international investment agreements with the public interest by using customary international law. This strategy draws attention to the conflict that

42 Morgan Bazilian, Victoria Cuming and Thomas Kenyon, ‘Local-Content Rules for Renewables Projects Don’t Always Work’ (2020) 32 *Energy Strategy Reviews* 100569.

43 Ibid.

44 Heather Elko McKibben and Shaina D Western, “‘Reserved Ratification’: An Analysis of States’ Entry of Reservations Upon Ratification of Human Rights Treaties’ (2020) 50 *British Journal of Political Science* 687.

exists between luring in foreign capital and defending domestic interests, as well as the changing conversation about state accountability in the context of international investment. Therefore, the treaty may not provide protection for an investment if it endangers national security. Foreign investors violating the fair and equitable treatment (FET) criterion may deter accusations of state culpability in delicate fields like armaments.⁴⁵ The equitable principle emphasizes responsible behavior in interactions between investors and host nations. This defense emphasizes the reciprocal nature of obligations within the investment framework, asserting that foreign investors have an equal obligation to respect local laws, human rights, and environmental standards, as well as host states' expectations of a stable and predictable investment environment.

Restraint on International Arbitration

African countries are shifting their approach to international investment agreements, limiting their commitments to international arbitration.⁴⁶ This is to attract global investment while pursuing broader social objectives. This strategy acknowledges that rigid arbitration clauses can hinder national interests, especially when foreign investors cause adverse social or environmental impacts. By retaining control over dispute resolution mechanisms, host states can prioritize local considerations and align investments with their developmental goals. This approach can enhance regulatory sovereignty, allowing African countries to engage with foreign investors on terms that reflect their unique socio-economic landscapes. This may lead to more sustainable and inclusive development.⁴⁷ South Africa's Protection of Investment Act (SAPIA) of 2015 prohibited investor-state arbitration and terminated many bilateral investment treaties.⁴⁸ Under the

45 August Reinisch and Christoph Schreuer (eds), 'Fair and Equitable Treatment', *International Protection of Investments: The Substantive Standards* (Cambridge University Press 2020) <<https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/international-protection-of-investments/fair-and-equitable-treatment/EF1F319BFFA4602F6C76F1D6FDED94EF>> accessed 30 September 2024.

46 Makane Moïse Mbengue and Stefanie Schacherer, 'Evolution of International Investment Agreements in Africa: Features and Challenges of Investment Law "Africanization"' in Julien Chaisse, Leïla Choukroune and Sufian Jusoh (eds), *Handbook of International Investment Law and Policy* (Springer 2021) <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-3615-7_77> accessed 30 September 2024.

47 EDIT, 'Cameroon - Turkey BIT (2012) - Electronic Database of Investment Treaties (EDIT)' <<https://edit.wti.org/document/show/37b29e9d-82c3-49a1-bbd2-35d46ee9214a?textBlockId=6e087fcb-1eba-4f57-b497-b76a978db272&page=1>> accessed 29 September 2024.: See, The 2012 Cameroon-Turkey Bilateral Investment Treaty prevents international arbitral review disputes arising from investments under 10% of a firm, unauthorized operations, and real estate rights.

48 Tarcisio Gazzini, 'Rethinking the Promotion and Protection of Foreign Investments: The 2015 South Africa's Protection Investment Act' (29 April 2017) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2960567>> accessed 30 September 2024.

SAPIA permits South Africa to accept foreign arbitration; however, the arbitration takes place between South Africa and the investor's home state rather than directly with the investor.⁴⁹

CONCLUSION

Despite the incredible expansion of Bilateral Investment Treaties (BITs) throughout Africa, their efficacy as legal instruments for advancing and protecting foreign investments has been considerably undermined. One notable illustration of this decline is the steep increase in investor-state dispute arbitrations at ICSID, which indicates a surge in contract violations by state parties. State parties have the right to disregard provisions in BITs and underlying agreements because of inherent contrasts between these interests.

The involvement of African state parties in IIAs has exposed a widespread pattern of noncompliance among contracting states with basic requirements inherent in the BITs. The formerly guaranteed protections provided to investors under the umbrella clause of these provides have been seriously called into question by this alarming trend. The interpretation of umbrella clauses is a controversial topic in the ongoing investment disputes between foreign investor and host stat.

49 Makane Moïse Mbengue and Mohamed H Negr, 'An African View on the CETA Investment Chapter' in Makane Moïse Mbengue and Stefanie Schacherer (eds), *Foreign Investment Under the Comprehensive Economic and Trade Agreement (CETA)* (Springer International Publishing 2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-98361-5_10> accessed 30 September 2024.